

CURRENT TRENDS AND DEVELOPMENT FACTORS IN THE APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATION

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Abstract: *Innovative behavior does not mean adaptation, it implies the formation of one's personality, one's self-development. The teacher needs to understand that innovative education is a way to nurture a well-rounded individual. "Ready templates" don't fit him, it's important to constantly improve your intellectual level. A teacher who gets rid of "complexes" and psychological barriers to become a full participant in innovative change ready*

Key Words: *Innovation Technologies, Modern educations, Gender pedagogy, Heuristic pedagogy, Compulsory pedagogy and androgogic pedagogy.*

INTRODUCTION

The development of modern education has given rise to a new direction - innovative activity. The term "innovative pedagogy" and its specific research appeared in Western Europe and the United States in the 60s of the twentieth century. S.M. Godnin, V.I. Zagvyazinski. Researched in the works of V.A. Kan-Kalik, N.V. Kuzmina, V.A. Slatenin, A.I. Sherbakov. These studies are highlighted in terms of innovative activity practices and the dissemination of best pedagogical practices. H. Barnet, J. Basset, D. Hamilton, N. Gross, M. Mayez, A. Haylock, D. Chen, R. Edem. »The necessary conditions for the psychological aspect of innovation was developed by E. Rodgers, one of the American innovative scientists. It's an innovation he studied the classification of the participants in the process, his attitude to the novelty, and his readiness to understand it. In the XXI century, which is considered to be the age of information and advanced technologies, the issue of widespread introduction of innovations in the educational process has received more and more attention. In Uzbekistan, in recent years, innovation was one of the first to enter the education system than in other areas, and we can see how innovation is reflected in the educational process. The introduction of innovation into the system of pedagogical sciences includes the following in the structure of pedagogical sciences:

- a) Gender pedagogy;
- b) Heuristic pedagogy;
- c) Compulsory pedagogy;
- g) was marked by the influx of disciplines such as androgogic pedagogy.

We can see the penetration of innovation in the teaching system in the content of education, teaching methods, forms of teaching, types of teaching, teaching aids.

- Innovation in the content of education is explained by the introduction of traditional, non-traditional and distance learning.

- We see the introduction of active, passive and interactive methods of innovation in teaching methods. While the use of the active method serves to increase the activity of students in the classroom process, the passive method is explained by giving students a one-sided understanding. The interactive method is understood to be an active collaboration (teacher with student, student with student).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

We can see the introduction of innovation in the form of lessons in the example of standard, non-standard and virtual forms of lessons.

- Innovation in the types of education is explained by the types of problem-based education, heuristic education, tiered education, integrated education, interactive education, informal education, formal education, non-formal education.

- We explain the introduction of innovation in teaching aids in the classroom with multimedia, electronic whiteboards and other tools.

- Innovation in teaching methods can be seen in the following methods.

1. Active method. This method encourages students to become more active in the classroom, to think about a particular situation and reality.

2. Passive method. This method leads to the formation of a one-sided understanding of the topic being studied by students during the course.

3. Interactive method. The purpose of this method is based on the active interaction of teachers and students during the lesson.

Innovation in the form of lessons can be seen in the following figure. a) Standard lesson - the structure within the lesson does not change. b) Non-standard lesson - the structure within the lesson changes. c) Virtual lesson - that is, distance learning. The concept of "New" plays a central role in pedagogical innovation. There is also an interest in private, conditional, local and subjective innovation in pedagogical science. Pedagogical innovation is the process of developing, implementing, testing and evaluating innovations in education that help to effectively achieve the set goals. Mutual: the educational process will change over time, the

labor market will place new demands on future workers and training will adapt to new goals, which will require new pedagogical methods, techniques and techniques .

News in the field of education will help to achieve the following goals:

✓ Humanization, the learning process

democratization;

Activation of students' cognitive activity;

Improving the effectiveness of the organization of educational and educational work;

✓ Methodology and didactics of educational material

change in perspective. Pedagogical innovation is based on two main approaches:

A student-centered approach involves focusing the learning process on each individual student. Modern pedagogy should take into account the unique experience and character of each student, develop his personality and talent. The implementation of this approach involves relying on the principles of choice (students can choose the field of their choice), confidence (lack of authoritarian pressure by teachers), creativity and success, subjectivity, individuality;

The authority-based approach is new to the Russian school. It focuses on the learning outcome, resulting in a set of skills rather than a set of knowledge, the student's ability to solve problems, conflict and act in different situations. It doesn't matter how much the student knows. Most importantly, his attitude to change, his flexibility, his ability to manage emotions and choose the right information. This innovation requires a radical overhaul of the education system, a reform of the principles of evaluation and organization of education. Based on these approaches, teachers and methodologists develop innovative pedagogical technologies - a set of methods, techniques and methods of knowledge transfer and assessment, which are introduced in educational institutions. Project work is a type of activity that helps to develop students' creative abilities and develop their teamwork skills. The purpose of the projects is to update and put into practice, expand and deepen the acquired knowledge. Work on the project can be individual, pair or micro-group, which involves solving the problem, finding optimal solutions. Schools actively use the integration of disciplines in projects, for example, they invite students to study the interdisciplinary links between language and literature, mathematics and chemistry, history and biology. This innovation shapes and develops the ability to think complexly, analyze, communicate and create new ideas, see a holistic picture of the world. The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a decree "On the activities of the Academy of Sciences, the organization of research work on measures to further improve the management, financing and financing of the project in 2017 Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan

No. PP-2789 of February 17, 2017 "On the implementation of measures to improve the organization, management and financing of research activities" May 19, 2017 302 Science and Technology of the Republic of Uzbekistan in accordance with the Resolution No. agency was established the main tasks and functions of the Agency Functions: socio-economic and socio-political implementation of measures to identify and implement priorities for the development of science and technology, taking into account the objectives of development and the achievements of modern science;

Systematic monitoring of the formation, implementation and implementation of state scientific and technical programs and the use of the results of research in the socio-economic development of the country; ensuring the implementation of important intersectoral scientific and technical programs;

- For sectors of the economy and the social sphere formation of state assignments in the provision of scientific and technical services for the implementation of fundamental, applied and innovative research;

- Organize the annual Republican Fair of Innovative Ideas, Technologies and Projects and monitor the implementation of agreements signed under it;

- Development of international cooperation in the field of science and technology, attraction of foreign investments and grants, organization of joint scientific and technical projects and innovative developments with foreign partners;

- Highly qualified scientific and scientific-pedagogical staff planning and coordination of training activities

Functions:

a) on the implementation of measures to identify and implement priorities for the development of science and technology, taking into account the objectives of socio-economic, socio-political development of the country and the achievements of modern science:

- . socio-economic, socio-political

develops proposals on priorities for the development of science and technology, taking into account the development objectives and achievements of modern science; make proposals to the State Commission to determine the strategy for the development of priority and promising areas of research and advanced technologies that ensure the development of society and the state; develops proposals to increase the effectiveness of funding mechanisms for research and development; ensures the implementation of programs approved by the State Commission in the field of further development of science, aimed at the rational allocation and effective use of scientific and technological potential, increasing the share of science and technology in the development of the state economy;

participates in the development of regulations in the field of scientific and technical, innovative activities and protection of intellectual property;

b) systematic monitoring of the formation, implementation and implementation of state scientific and technical programs and the use of the results of research in the socio-economic development of the country: State scientific and technical programs of fundamental, applied and innovative research on the basis of state assignments approved by the State Commission for the implementation of research and development work forms projects; . fundamental, applied research and innovation concludes contracts with research, educational institutions and other institutions of the republic for the implementation of scientific and technical projects in the framework of state scientific and technical programs; conducts systematic monitoring of the implementation of state scientific and technical programs; Based on the analysis of the results of monitoring of state scientific and technical programs, proposals to the State Commission on the withdrawal of vacant funds from the state scientific and technical programs of inefficient, obsolete scientific and technical projects, redirected to the most effective and relevant scientific and technical projects enters;

c) on ensuring the implementation of important intersectoral scientific and technical programs:

- Uzbekistan in the field of scientific and technical activities Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Kazakhstan, state and economic administration bodies and others coordinates the activities of organizations;

- Implement joint science projects integration and interaction of academic and network science with higher education institutions in order to increase implements measures;

- Science, education and development for technology transfer implements a set of measures to promote the integration of the extractive sector;

g) formation of state assignments in the provision of scientific and technical services for the implementation of fundamental, applied and innovative research for sectors of the economy and the social sphere:

- state and economic administration bodies, local forms a draft state order for research, development and technological and innovative developments on the basis of proposals from public authorities and other organizations;

- state and economic administration bodies, local organizes interdepartmental scientific and technical councils to organize the analysis and examination of proposals of public authorities and other organizations;

- For sectors of the economy and the social sphere make proposals based on the State Commission for approval of state assignments for the provision of scientific and technical services for the implementation of fundamental, applied and innovative research;

Innovative educational technology is a new and qualitative improvement of teaching and learning activities, including the improvement of existing methods and tools to increase the efficiency of the educational process and create the best conditions for teaching and learning activities. methodology of organization. current trends in the socio-economic development of society. Innovations in education include a set of measures aimed at the emergence of innovations in education. These innovations can be methods and techniques of organizing the educational process, resources used in the process of education and upbringing, scientific theories and concepts.

CONCLUSION

Innovation is a kind of new scientific knowledge aimed at obtaining discoveries, inventions through the use of research activities develops. In addition, innovation emergence may be the result of design work, which develops instrumental and technological knowledge that reflects the ability to perform practical actions on the basis of existing scientific theories and concepts. Thus, innovative projects are created, which then leads to the emergence of new technologies. Innovations are also in the process of educational activities develops. Students in the learning process develops theoretical and practical knowledge, then they are innovations of practical life can be applied in various fields related to the creation. The importance of innovation in education Innovative technologies in education allow to regulate education and direct it in the right direction. People were always afraid of the unknown and new things, they were negative about any change. Stereotypes that exist in the public mind, affecting the usual way of life, lead to painful events, preventing the renewal of all forms of education. The reason why people are reluctant to accept innovations in modern education is that they are blocking vital needs for convenience, security and self-affirmation. Not everyone is ready to re-learn theory, take an exam, change their mind, spend personal time and money. Once the update process has started, you can only stop it using special methods.

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